

Health and social care provision to people living with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: Phase 1 Report

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Scotland Centre
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*This work is supported by
The Dunhill Medical Trust
(Grant number RPGF/2006\236)*

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About the study

This mixed methods study aimed to identify and develop new and effective ways to improve the health and well-being of the increasing numbers of older people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison.

Twenty semi-structured interviews were completed with staff to identify the current ways people with a suspected dementia were identified, referred, diagnosed and provided with post-diagnostic care in four prisons in Scotland with the largest number of people over 65 years (Phase 1).

The staff who participated included nurses based in prison healthcare centres, prison social workers, sessional support staff such as GPs, psychologists and forensic psychiatrists, Scottish prison service staff and staff contracted by the Scottish prison services to provide personal care.

Through interviews with a further four staff and five men living with diagnosed or suspected dementia and data from the healthcare records of the five men we gained an in-depth picture into their lived care experience (Phase 2).

This understanding informed the co-production of an evidence informed model of care and care pathway that inform and improve pre and post diagnostic care for people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison (Phase 3).

Why this study is important

Prisoners with a suspected or diagnosed dementia are becoming an increasing concern to prison services and prison healthcare staff due to the complexity of their health and social care needs. There is very little known about this population or how they are cared for in Scotland. Suggestions for how to care for this marginalised group needs to move beyond speculation if we are to develop new effective ways to improve their health and well-being.

The number of people over 60 years of age trebled in UK prisons between 2002 and 2016. Recent data from England (Forsyth et al. 2020) suggested a much higher prevalence of dementia in prisons than found among community populations of the same age.

Improved ways of recognising and managing the increasing number of older prisoners with complex health needs including dementia is urgent. The consequences of not doing so may heighten fear and distress, reduce opportunities to access appropriate healthcare interventions and support, and violate human rights.

This study offers a model of care to develop evidence informed approaches to timely identification and diagnosis that would have many benefits to people with dementia and those who support them. It offers a co-produced evidence-informed care pathway that could serve as a tool for change that would enable the right care, at the right time, by the right people, and provide an opportunity to assess risk and plan care for the future.

About the phase 1 report

This report is the first in a series of five reports. It focuses on the findings of phase 1 of the larger study described above. It presents the findings from twenty interviews with staff from the four prisons in Scotland that house the highest number of men over 65 years.

The interviews explored the current ways people with suspected dementia were identified and diagnosed, how their health and social care needs were met, what dementia education staff had and felt they needed. This report provides some concluding points from phase 1, the recommendations arising from the entire study are in the final report and the lay summary.

The other reports from the study can be found below:

1. Case studies of people with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in prison: **Phase 2 Report**
2. Co-designed evidenced informed healthcare pathways for people living with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in Scottish prisons: **Phase 3 Report**
3. The health and social care of people living with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: **Final Project Report**
4. The health and social care of people living with diagnosed or suspected dementia in prison: **Final Lay Report**

Findings

Identification, screening and assessment

There was no standardised way of identifying people with a suspected dementia within and across the four prisons. The national screening programme for prisons in Scotland does not currently include cognitive screening for older prisoners.

The reports from staff and case studies suggested that the healthcare staff were reliant on those living in or working more closely with prisoners alerting them to concerns. This appeared to mean that the identification of those with suspected cognitive impairment or dementia was largely reliant on prison officers, prisoners, external carers or staff undertaking other assessments with the person such as social workers.

“Sometimes we have very little contact, if they aren't on supervised medications, we might never meet them. It's a health centre within a prison, it's not that we're nurses on the halls providing care. It is very much we're here for treatment rooms, emergencies and dispensing meds. So, we don't have a lot of input up on the halls. The community carers, they bring a lot of stuff to our attention, because they spend the majority of time with these guys. And the SPS staff. So they would all be part of identifying it”.

Prison 3: Primary Care Nurse 1

Recognising changes in presentation even if the person had been in prison for many months, was not always straightforward. Many of the older men tended to stay in their cells.

There is no universally accepted definition of old age in prisons, the most common threshold is 50 years, though the Scottish Prison service use the threshold of 55 years. These lower thresholds are based on evidence that suggests the health-related needs of prisoners are advanced by around 10 years, relative to people in the general population (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2021)

The invisibility of older men echoes the findings of previous reports on older prisoners such as 'Old and Quiet' (HMIPS 2004), 'Who Cares' (HMIPS, 2017) and 'No place for old men' (Ridley 2021).

“It's quite a fragmented process. It could be signs of deterioration could be missed for quite a period of time, particularly within our older population, because a lot of them are quite quiet.”

Prison 3: Social Worker

To begin the diagnostic process, initial screening in NHS settings usually involves a brief interview alongside administration of cognitive screening tool. The Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) is considered one of the best short cognitive screening tools, superior to the Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) because it is more comprehensive in the cognitive domains it tests (Roalf et al. 2013), on a practical note, the MoCA is free to NHS staff to use. The MoCA was also found to be more accurate than the 6-item Cognitive Impairment Test at indicating Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) or dementia in a prison population (Forsyth et al 2020). However, the recent SIGN 168 guideline found no evidence to recommend one cognitive test over another, rather selection should consider adequate accuracy for identifying dementia, ease of administration and interpretation, cost and training requirements (2023). Once initial screening has been performed and the scores indicate poor cognitive functioning it is usual that a more extensive cognitive screening tool such as the Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination, third revision (ACE-III), is administered. Cognitive tests can identify the need for specialist input to help with a diagnosis of dementia. These tools are not diagnostic on their own but can be used to identify people who might benefit from referral for specialist dementia assessment (SIGN, 2023). The accuracy of the ACE-III in non-specialist settings has not yet been established (Beishon et al 2019). The national screening programme for prisons in Scotland does not currently include cognitive screening for older prisoners.

If the healthcare staff were alerted that a person may have cognitive issues, the mental nurse nurses undertook the initial cognitive screening. The tools they used varied across the four prisons. Although there was an awareness amongst all the health care staff of the cognitive screening tools available and in use they did not express any clinical knowledge or preference about them. If initial cognitive screening indicated more extensive cognitive screening and assessment was required, the mental health nurses, sometimes in conjunction with the GPs, would gather more in-depth health histories and conduct further tests and involve the sessional forensic psychiatrist.

“We would do your cognitive assessments, ACE, the MMSE, we've got the lengthy history, and then from those findings we would discuss it with the psychiatrist and then refer to the older adult psychiatrist, who would then come and make the appointment”.

Prison 2: Mental Health Nurse

Assessing dementia in this population was often complex and lengthy, related to a lack of clarity around the processes of referral and assessment and access to community health services. Staff in all four prisons reported that there was no formal healthcare pathway for staff to follow that would guide the referral and assessment process. A 'case by case approach' was adopted.

“Everything is a rough guide here, no designated care pathway for these individuals. It would be very much dependent on the person and how they're presenting and what kind of professional assessments would be available at the time. So not standardised but through the goodwill of all the team, we tend have a clinical care package but it's not identified, the exact pathway, no”.

Prison 1: GP2

The point in the assessment process that the four prison healthcare teams referred to old age psychiatry varied as did the support they received from old age psychiatry services across the different Health boards. For example, one community old age psychiatry service had declined a referral put in by the prison healthcare team on the grounds that they did provide a service to people in prison. Whereas another prison healthcare team reported during phase 2, they had put in place a newly established an assessment and referral pathway with their local old age psychiatry team. This is perhaps unsurprising given that Cognitive clinics (also referred to as memory clinics), which provide clinical assessment for individuals with cognitive complaints or suspected neurodegenerative disease have been found to have no

standardised approach to the assessment of these and variation in the implementation of assessment and care pathways (SIGN 168, 2023).

In this study, prison healthcare staff felt unsure about what the referral and assessment process should be and their role within it.

“There is no clear pathway for us. And it's an emerging problem. It's something that is not going to go away. We're getting more and more people referred to us. And we're by no means experts in dementia. We need to have a document or a flowchart, that could maybe have, 'this is who we contact, this is what we do, these are the next steps.' Just that simplified process that we know who the players are. For example, the gentleman at the moment that we have, we missed a process. We had to go back to the beginning again, and it wasn't the prison that missed the process, it was ourselves, the NHS, because we're not quite sure of what to do about adults with incapacity”.

Prison 4: Mental Health Nurse 1

Referrals to healthcare from prison staff tended to be vague about the nature of the problem. The healthcare teams responded by taking a collaborative approach to assessing a person's health and social needs.

“They're (prison staff) used to that, they've seen people go into withdrawals from drugs and alcohol, and people being unwell. So, they will flag it up to the nursing staff to say, you know, 'this person's not quite right.' And then the primary care nurses might get involved. If it's thought to be something chronic or cognitive then the mental health. And then we can often work in partnership to say, right, we can do physical tests if they think it could be bloods or something else. Psychiatry have asked on occasions that we do CT scans, just to rule out, you know, some sort of weird brain injury, you know, for somebody's behaviour”.

Prison 4: GP2

Access to other types of professional assessments that may be helpful in providing a full picture of a person's health and social care needs varied from prison to prison.

“It would be myself that would refer them for OT or PT, sight, hearing, speech and language, any of those if it's necessary, I'll have to refer them onto the hospital. And the social care assistant, I think, SPS. The nurses can list them for the optician, but the rest I have to refer them on. I have to refer them out for OT, nothing on site in this prison, there's not even physio on site here. But the optician's come in. I try and get the team involved and make sure that the medication becomes supervised. And let the SPS know”.

Prison 1: Mental Health Nurse

The need for prison healthcare staff to refer to community teams for input or assessment was common as specialist services such as occupational therapy (for people aged over 65 years), physiotherapy, speech and language therapy, audiology and old age psychiatry were not available within the prisons that participated in this study. One prison healthcare team did have occupational therapists onsite; however, these roles were age specific and did not extend to covering people over 65 years. Another had rehabilitation support worker roles within the healthcare team. In the community these roles are about supporting quality of life through assessing care and support needs, advising on how to use specialist equipment, teaching life skills and organising activities.

Prison health care

The start of the millennium saw reform of prison health across the UK, with prison healthcare services being transferred to the NHS Scotland in 2011. This was in an effort to reduce health inequalities and ensure individuals in prison receive equitable and integrated health and social care.

The prison population have poorer health than community populations across a several domains (Gilling MacIntosh et al., 2023), with significantly higher rates of traumatic brain injury (TBI) (Williams and Kent, 2021), drug and alcohol abuse (Fazel et al. 2017), mental health problems such as depression (Rebbapragada et al. 2021, Mental Welfare Commission, 2022) and other long term health conditions. It is also thought that socially produced 'ageing' is apparent in prison populations (Stojkovic, 2007). Although the NHS and Local authorities commonly used 65 years to define older age, the age thresholds vary across prison services differ. The Scottish Prison Service consider 55 years of age a reasonable threshold for classifying a person as older (SPS 2017). Older people in prison have very high rates of chronic physical health problems, with 80% aged 60-64 years reporting at least one moderate or severe illness, increasing to 92% of those over 70 years (Hayes et al., 2012).

A recent report pointed to the lack of correlation between the size of the prison, the mental health needs of its population and the number and type of mental health staff available to meet identified needs (Mental Welfare Commission 2022). Moreover, they suggested the while reforms have brought different health structures and processes the challenge of addressing health inequalities and equivalency of provision remains (RCN 2016, MWC 2022, Scottish Government 2022, HMIPs 2022). We also found evidence that working within prison healthcare raised particular challenges around accessing equitable care for people with a suspected dementia.

"I've gone through cycles of challenging the referral process. I did a standard referral through Old Age Psychiatry in the same manner I did only a few months earlier in the community for a similar gentleman. My community gentleman ended up being assessed, whereas my patient in prison within twenty-four hours, an e-mail following a telephone call to the health centre, came through: "We just don't see patients in prison." These should be referred to the forensic psychiatrists. In a prison health care setting, a lot of our patients have mental health issues and don't have access to psychiatry as much as they should. People with a specialty should be working with a client and diagnosing it. Just as if somebody needed a cardiologist, they need a cardiologist. So that was disappointing though very unsurprising to me. But that case was a classic example of a referral that didn't deviant in one way from a similar referral in the community with two separate outcomes".

Prison 1: GP2

Meeting complex health and social care needs

Concerns about how to meet the complex health and social care needs of the increasing older population in prison is heightening (HMIPs 2022). Our data shines a light on how the complex health and social needs of people living with dementia in prison also needs urgent attention.

To try and better meet health and social care needs the prisons involved in this study tended to accommodate older men and those with health and social care needs together as much as possible. They also tried to allocate prison officers who had more experience and or interest in working with this population to those areas. All the staff we spoke to felt that most prison officers were good at helping those under their care and establishing good relationships. Prison staff who worked in the residential areas and fellow prisoners were those who most often provided social support. The extent to which prison officers became involved in providing social care and support varied between prisons and prison officers. This was related to whether the prison had external carers coming in, whether there was a prisoner carer system in place and the prison officers themselves.

Only one of the prisons involved in the study had a formal prisoner carer system in place. The staff we spoke to in this prison felt the carer system worked well and found it reassuring that the person was getting assistance over and above the personal care provided by the external carers. Many staff in the other prisons reported that prisoners did this type of caring informally. Usually for the older frailer men by letting staff know if the person was struggling, offering to take them out in the wheelchair for some fresh air, take their meal trays to them, or help them get around the residential area.

A recent report by the Scottish Government into the social care needs of people in prison stated that social care should include support with activities of daily living, maintaining independence, managing personal relationships, taking part in prison life, and social interaction (Scottish Government 2021). Our findings suggest that the role of external carers who were contracted by the prison service focussed on supporting

individuals with personal needs such as bathing, using the toilet, getting dressed, eating as identified by the nurses.

“As primary care nurses we implement care plans, if they need carers to come in and help them get washed and dressed, it's us that implement that, and then give it to the hall staff and they can arrange for the carers to come. We can refer them to external and the chaplaincy. If they need like a soft food diet or anything, we can do that. So, we would initially have a like a meeting with the prisoner, identify any needs. Sometimes you'll find the hall staff can help in that sense, if they've noticed the prisoner's not be going for a shower for so many days, or they've not changed their bed for so many days. So, it's wee things you can identify on our care plans. And then we just pass a copy onto the hall staff, and it's them that arrange the carers to come in. And the carers just go off the copy of the care plan that we give them. It's always happened without an issue. And it always happens quite quick as well, actually. Usually within that same week, it's all done”.

Prison 1: Primary Care Nurse

The external carers were highly thought of by all staff. They could only provide the personal care specified in the care plan, if a person's care needs escalate and the care plan is not updated by the nursing staff to reflect increased care needs, they are unable to provide a higher level of care. Requests for equipment such as hoists or commodes to be provided or serviced could take time. The carers reported that once a care plan was in place issues such as high turnover of nursing staff and breakdowns in communication could affect their ability to carry out appropriate levels of personal care.

“Yes, we do the personal care and if we notice things we will take a note, write that on a slip and give that to the nurses, then we chase them up or maybe another prisoner tells us and we pass that on to the nurses. Some (nurses) are fine and they speak to you, others don't. If there was more continuity of staff, it would make it a little bit easier. But the man that needs assistance to stand, we've asked for the care plan to be updated, we need to get permission to provide what we think he needs but if it's not in the care plan we can't. We had to fight for months to get a hoist serviced before we could use it with that particular man. I needed to jump up and down and keep passing it on. Usually, it's because they need more assistance, it can take us a few weeks to get it changed. Sometimes we feel like we're chasing our tail. It would be nice to know what is wrong with the gentleman who can no longer walk, if we were in the community they would tell us, but we still don't know what is wrong. We might be able to help him better if we knew”.

Prison 4: Carer 2

It was clear that a small number of individuals required very high levels of support with personal care 24 hours a day. Care needs included continence care, support to wash, dress, go to the toilet, eat, drink and mobilise.

“One of the men doesn't have capacity, and he has very, very impaired mobility. He is unable to get out of bed, he needs round the clock care now. He deteriorated really quite rapidly. He's not at end-of-life care yet. But he's got his anticipatory care plan, and I think he's got a 'do not attempt resuscitation' as well. We now have carers coming in during the night. They're in bed for prolonged periods of time, they need turning, they need monitoring for... not just for pressure area care, but for urinary and bowel problems that... the things that you would expect as somebody becomes more and more frail, and less and less mobile. And more and more confused”.

Prison 3: Mental Health Nurse

Sometimes managing staff safety took precedence over providing personal care, particularly when there were staff shortages.

“To be honest with you, we don't really get much quality time with that person because he poses too high a risk, he's too unpredictable. He doesn't make eye contact with anybody, his head's down and he sort of grasps at his tee-shirt at the bottom as if it's a kind of soother, and a comfort thing. And he'll walk, and he'll just keep walking, and he'll do this for hours on end, every day. I don't engage with him, it's not because I don't want to, it's because I kind of don't feel safe, because any time I've engaged with him, we aren't allowed to go into the section without a member of SPS staff. And again, you're looking at staffing as well. They might not have the staff to allow for that. With a shortage of staff, prison staff, prison-based staff, NHS staff, it's quite... we're just kind of.. I'm not saying winging it, but sometimes it feels you're winging it, do you know what I mean? You're trying to give really good patient care, but you struggle sometimes. I sometimes feel we're quite ill equipped. And we're trying to do the best we can, with the resources that we've got. But we really could be doing more”.

Prison 3: Carer 2

Staff reported that they felt they were relying on good will rather than adequately staffed teams and effective and efficient systems and processes. At the time of phase 1 data collection three out of the four prisons had monthly multiagency health care meetings to discuss and review 'people of concern'. Prison staff with a management or leadership role, e.g., unit managers, Deputy Governors/Governors along with a range of NHS staff would attend these meetings.

One prison had a multidisciplinary team (MDT) meeting that covered mental and physical health, another had separate monthly MDT meetings for physical and mental health and another had one for mental health. One healthcare team had been trying for several years to set up a regular multi-agency healthcare meeting that included the prison service to discuss those with high health and care needs. Although the healthcare team met regularly to discuss and review patients, prison staff did not attend so the communication was via ad-hoc meetings between healthcare staff and unit managers.

The healthcare staff felt that regular multi-agency meetings would facilitate better communication and understanding of everyone's role in the care and support of individuals. They felt this lack of 'buy-in' from senior prison staff affected working relationships between prison and NHS staff. An example they provided was that prison staff requested support from the healthcare team with a man who frequently became disorientated. The healthcare team had given the prison staff some written guidance about how to reorient the man. However, the prison staff were resistant to use the guidance as they felt it wasn't their job and wanted the healthcare staff to do it. In the moment reorientation would need to be carried out by staff who worked in the areas where the men were accommodated.

Many staff talked about the need for improved processes, they also felt better multidisciplinary working and education for staff were other ways to improve care and support for older people and people with dementia in prison.

“So if there was a process in place giving them numbers of older people that we're looking after, that could enhance us getting involved in supporting people with dementia and other MCIs. A lot of the time the environment can obviously mask someone's presentation. So it's a bit about improving your multi-agency staff group's awareness, education and having a better integrated process where we're all responsible for, but that's not happening for the older people that we look after”.

Prison 3: Primary Care Nurse 2

The NHS staff were very aware that activities and supports to promote health and well-being that are available to most people in the community such as dementia advisors, meeting places, resource centres, cafes, reminiscence groups, choirs, etc. were not available to those in prison. The Scottish Government Local Delivery Plan standard states that every person diagnosed with dementia should get one year of post diagnostic support (PDS) coordinated by a named link worker¹. None of the staff we spoke to used this terminology or were aware of the Government standard for PDS or the PDS models used to inform this work.

The built environment of prisons is not designed to accommodate individuals with poor physical health and disabilities (Scottish Government 2022). The limited availability of accessible cells often meant staff were put in a position of making decisions about who, out of those who required an accessible cell, needed it most. Those with the required the highest level of assistance with personal care tended to be prioritised. This situation also presents challenges for the provision of social care in prisons (Scottish Government, 2021).

¹Less than half of people 42.9% (n= 8,144) newly diagnosed with dementia were referred for PDS in the community in 2019/20 (ISD, 2022).

“There are accessibility cells but there aren't enough of them. Whoever designed them didn't have these people in mind, they are difficult work in. And we really struggle with the way the cells are, they are not made for someone who's got mobility issues. I mean we try our best to kind of reorganize the cells but there isn't much we can do. There is one accessible on this floor, there aren't usually modifications made to normal cells for someone with dementia. The only difference between that cell and the others is the shower. The space is quite narrow but still it's a good thing to have your own shower rather than having to move them to the communal showers were there is one for disabled people. We can put people with wheelchairs in there, so that's the only facility they've got. I mean that is for those with a disability, not necessarily for dementia. The tragedy is we have more than one who needs an accessible cell, they try and put them in single cells as much as they can. Can't have someone with dementia or disability in the same cell as a younger fit man, it's not fair on any of them for dignity and privacy reasons. This isn't the right place for them when they need 24-hour care”.

Prison 4: Carer 1

Common adaptations included getting a hospital bed and grab rails in situ. To get other adaptations in place often involved the input of an external occupational therapist or physiotherapist, the healthcare teams would then make recommendations to the prison service based on those assessments. We found one team who had used colour and contrast to support the independence of two men.

“Modified accommodation... we're very limited. Signage, we do have a couple of guys who we put coloured tape round their door, so they can identify it. We have one of the patients with the dementia, we changed the colour of the paint. Other changes, we would provide some equipment. Things like non-slip surface material, the surfaces in their cell are quite light, so we got a dark blue colour so we could sit their plates and things on it, so they could identify it, because they were struggling to see it. We put in grab rails”.

Prison 3: Carer 1

In two of the prisons the residential areas had some high back chairs with arm rests, to enable those with limited mobility sit outside of their cell and move between chairs.

Accommodating individual needs to prevent or minimise stress and distress was particularly challenging during periods of enforced restricted regimes, where individuals are locked up for long periods of time, as was common during COVID 19, when there were staff shortages or lock downs. Prison staff tried to adapt regimes (if COVID restrictions and staffing allowed) to allow people who became distressed when locked in their cell out to walk about during periods where other people may be locked up. This was a clear attempt to prevent or minimise the person getting distressed. However, prison officers were there primarily to manage risk and safety.

“I suppose another hindrance was the prisoner's behaviours. Albeit we have small pockets of guys with this kind of early on stages of dementia and cognitive ability, but rightly or wrongly you treat a kind of violent prisoner as a violent prisoner, you've got to kind of look at the health and safety of the staff as paramount. And I think it's about providing more awareness to staff regarding the background of each individual, as opposed to just seeing it as it's somebody being angry and shouting, but it's difficult, massively difficult”.

Prison 3: Prison Officer

Staff reported that occasionally people with dementia, if they were very agitated and perceived as a threat to the health and safety of staff, were restrained and locked in their cell. When a person with dementia become extremely distressed, prison staff tried to talk to the person and manage the situation as best they could. Healthcare staff who witnessed these situations described feeling “awful” and “heartbroken”. These situations also illustrated the differing ethos and priorities of prison and healthcare staff (Dhaliwal & Hirst, 2016). Some staff reflected on the reforms to prison healthcare and suggested these may have introduced tensions and divisions.

“It's very difficult as a nurse to be able to actually carry out your job to the best that you can because of the nature of the prison. I don't know if every prison's the same, but it just sort of seems to be becoming more of a divide. I think because it used to be like the nurses were all SPS, they were all officers as well and I think ever since the NHS has taken over that and obviously NHS has got its own protocols and processes and things that we have to do, I think that sort of gets a lot of people's backs up. “Well, it's a prison, you'll kind of do what we say...” It's a very difficult place to work (laugh).”

Prison 3: Primary Care Nurse 2

Leaving prison

People leaving prison encounter many difficulties accessing a range of supports such as housing, benefits and GP registration, this is likely to be exacerbated for those with limited mobility, mental illness, and a disability (Scottish Government, 2021). On liberation people may not be going back to the area they lived in previously or may not know where they are going to stay until the day of liberation. Registration with a GP prior to liberation was not possible. If a person had been in prison less than 3 months they could go back to their own GP, otherwise they needed to apply to register with a GP who would then be allocated to them, this process could take days or weeks.

“So we're hamstrung by the fact that we can't register with GPs before they're liberated, so we can't do a good hand over of care. We can just invite the GP to get a mandate, to get in touch with us, or to give recommendations on the discharge letter, and hope that the patient retains it, and gives it to the new GP. Because if they've got a determinate sentence, they've got no follow-up if they choose not to have voluntary through-care. And we can't involve their relatives, because often their relatives don't want anything to do with them, and because of confidentiality. We can't pass it on”.

Prison 3: Carer Mental Health Nurse

When people's dementia advanced to point that they had complex, round the clock healthcare needs and were routinely becoming extremely distressed, the prison healthcare teams began looking for alternative accommodation. When a person was due for release or required to be transferred, their health and social care needs and risk to the public needed to be assessed. Assessing the risk to the public of a person with dementia in these circumstances was fraught with difficulty and complexity.

“It (release planning) starts to become very complicated from our point of view, because we’re looking up what’s the nature of our client? What’s he actually in prison for? How are we also responding to risk? So it’s not just as simple forward saying, ‘oh gosh, he’s got dementia.’ We’re still having to think about what’s this individual’s response? How do we protect the public? the risk of re-offending. We’re having to worry about welfare needs and risk”.

Prison 1: Social Worker

Multidisciplinary meetings would discuss the care needs, the risk the person posed to the public and whether the person would have sufficient capacity to follow the conditions of their release. Assessing capacity is not necessarily straightforward, as capacity can fluctuate, and a person may have capacity to make some decisions but not others. If a person was deemed not to have capacity the risk they posed to the public may be considered greater. Finding and securing alternative accommodation for people living with advanced dementia, with a criminal conviction (even if spent) was challenging as few alternatives were available.

“I know guys that are on like end of life care and stuff, they can get transferred out to hospital or hospices, I don’t know what the process would be for someone with like end of life like kind of last stages of dementia. So it’s difficult because we can’t transfer out for psychiatry”.

Prison 1: Mental Health Nurse

Suitable alternative accommodation may not be in Scotland. We were made aware of one man, due to the nature of his support needs, required to be transferred to a specialist NHS unit in England. As this unit only accepts transfers from other NHS facilities the man had to be first transferred to a secure forensic setting before the cross-border transfer could take place.

However, there were some people on Lifelong Orders who would never be eligible for release. These individuals would remain in prison unless they required acute hospital care, if they no longer required acute hospital care they would be returned to the prison.

Dementia education

The dementia education staff had received varied within and between staff groups. None of the staff had received any dementia education in their current role. Moreover, none of the NHS staff were aware of the NHS Education for Scotland (NES) Promoting Excellence dementia education resources freely available to all health and social care staff.

The GPs, who described themselves as generalists, all reported having had little or no specific dementia education in their first professional training or since they qualified. The psychologists and psychiatrists had experience of working clinically during their training with people who had a suspected dementia or diagnosed dementia. However, they described themselves as forensic specialists and did not feel educationally equipped in the care and management of dementia.

“These old folk in prison, just we’re all a bit clueless what you do with them. And this case has caused a lot of concern. And because I’m just a session a week, and I’m not an old age psychiatrist. So I was emailing old age psychiatry colleagues saying, ‘what do you think we should do medicine wise?’, we’re always told, try and stick within your area of expertise, so you’re acutely aware that you don’t want to cause more harm. But yeah, I think visiting sessions, or a couple of sessions a month, might be useful given the numbers are going up”.

Prison 4: Psychiatrist

The external carers reported having many years of on-the-job experience working with people living with a dementia and 'basic' dementia training from their current and past employers. The prison officers reported having had no dementia education during or since their training. The nursing staff reported having had some dementia education in their first professional training. Some had done some online dementia education modules since qualifying and some had post qualification experience of working with older people and or people living with a dementia. However, none of them felt they had expertise in working with older people or people living with a dementia.

“We're not experienced in the area, we can only do it when something occurs, like 'oh hang on a minute, we have to modify this or put this in place.' So we're learning, and when you're dealing with people, you shouldn't be learning, we should have things in place for them. But we can't plan for every eventuality, we can only do what we can. So yeah, there's multiple complexities and we absolutely struggle and need more help in these areas”.

Prison 4: Mental Health Nurse 2

All the staff felt dementia education for all NHS, prison and external care staff would be useful. They identified three areas in relation to dementia knowledge and skills that they felt they needed in order for them to feel more equipped to support people with a suspected or diagnosed dementia in a prison setting.

First, increasing their knowledge and understanding about the how best to identify, manage, and support people in prison who are living with a suspected or diagnosed dementia.

Second, education should be interdisciplinary, to increase awareness of disciplinary perspectives, expertise, roles and responsibilities within a multidisciplinary approach.

Third, educational content should include simulation exercises to increase understanding about what a person may be experiencing

“I think maybe nurses maybe think, 'Oh, well that's for mental health to deal with.' But I think everybody, all the primary care, rehab support, HCAs, I think everybody should be getting trained and having sort of an awareness of the management of people with dementia and cognitive decline. I think it would be beneficial to have the training, where you sort of are in the shoes of someone with dementia to see what they see, to hear what they hear, to sort of know how they feel.”

Prison 3: Primary Care Nurse 1

Some staff felt dementia awareness for people in prison would also be useful, the rationale being fellow prisoners may pick up signs or changes sooner than staff. Staff also felt that given the complexity associated with diagnosing, delivering care and planning release, access to staff in the community with dementia expertise would be advantageous.

Summary of findings

There was no standardised way of identifying people with a suspected dementia within and across the four prisons.

The national screening programme for prisons in Scotland does not currently include cognitive screening for older prisoners. If a person was brought to the attention of healthcare team, the mental health nurses carried out cognitive screening and history taking in consultation with a sessional forensic psychiatrist or GP.

Staff reported that assessing a person for dementia was often particularly complex due to several intersecting issues related to the poor health of prison population, a lack of clarity around the processes of referral and assessment and the nature of and resources afforded to providing healthcare in a prison setting.

Staff in all four prisons reported that there was no formal healthcare pathway for staff to follow that would guide the referral and assessment process and staff roles within it. A 'case by case approach' was adopted.

The staff reported workforce shortages, particularly amongst mental health nurses and there was some limited availability of sessional staff such as psychologists, forensic psychiatrists. The need for prison healthcare staff to refer to community teams was common as specialist services such as occupational therapy (for people aged over 65 years), physiotherapy, speech and language therapy, audiology and old age psychiatry were not available within the prisons that participated in this study.

The differing age thresholds between prison and community (NHS and Local Authority) further complicated access to specialist services. Prison healthcare teams reported that community teams responded to requests, albeit the wait times could be lengthy. Although, a request for input from a community old age psychiatry team had been refused

on the grounds that they did provide a service to people in prison. This perhaps illustrates the lack of standardised approach to the assessment of individuals with cognitive complaints or suspected neurodegenerative disease in memory clinics across Scotland (SIGN 168, 2023). These issues often meant assessment processes could be lengthy and disjointed.

The staff were aware that activities and supports to promote health and well-being available to many people living with dementia in the community were not available to those in prison. None of the staff were aware of Scottish Government Local Delivery Plan standard on post diagnostic support (PDS) or the PDS models being used to inform this work in the community. None of the staff were aware of the National Education for Scotland (NES) Promoting Excellence dementia education resources freely available to all staff working in health and social care settings.

Personal care was provided by external carers contracted by SPS. If there was a shortage or high turnover of nursing staff, there could be delays in updating personal care plans which are important for ensuring the consistency and coordination of care. There were very few accessible cells. Common adaptations were hospital beds, grab rails, commodes, and high back chairs. Normal cells tended not to be adapted. One prison had implemented several enabling features for two men who needed support with wayfinding, eating and mobilising.

Prison staff tried to adapt regimes (if COVID restrictions and staffing allowed) to allow people who became distressed when locked in their cell out to walk about during periods where other people may be locked up. However, prison officers were there primarily to manage risk and safety and there were reports that occasionally people with dementia, who were very agitated, and perceived as a threat to the health and safety of staff were restrained.

When people's dementia advanced to point that they had complex, round the clock healthcare needs and were routinely becoming distressed, the prison healthcare teams began looking for alternative accommodation. Involving the person in discussions about transition is likely to be difficult at this stage, it would be more possible in the context of an anticipatory care planning discussion at an earlier point. Finding suitable accommodation and assessing the risk to the public of a person with dementia that was due for release or required to be transferred was fraught with difficulty and complexity.

Merits and limitations

This study included four of the 15 prisons in Scotland, selected on the basis that they housed the largest numbers of men over 65 years.

This is justifiable as age is an important risk factor for dementia and it follows that dementia-related needs are more likely to be concentrated within these four sites.

Although the sampling strategy may reduce the generalisability of findings, it nonetheless provides evidence critical to understanding the adequacy of current approaches to the meeting dementia-related needs within the prison setting. There are known variations across the prison estate in terms of the healthcare needs of each prison population, the profile and numbers in each prison healthcare team and their approach to identification, assessment, referral and diagnosis of people with suspected cognitive impairment or dementia.

However, this study is, to the best of our knowledge, the first in Scotland to explore how people with a suspected cognitive impairment or dementia are identified, assessed, referred and diagnosed in prisons. It is also the first to explore the educational needs of prison and NHS staff in relation to this population. It provides a robust evidence base to inform ways to support staff and improve care for this population.

Concluding points

1. Consideration should be given to resourcing the introduction of brief cognitive screening to those convicted and 55 years and over.
2. All staff administering cognitive screening should undertake the free online training.
3. Consent to share should be sought early to streamline the sharing of information within and between prison, NHS and partner agencies.
4. Education about ageing and dementia should be mandatory. All staff should be encouraged to use the dementia education resources in the NHS for Education Promoting Excellence Dementia Knowledge and Skills framework appropriate to their role.
5. Consideration should be given to implementing a care pathway that guides the processes of screening, referral, assessment and post diagnostic care.
6. Each prison should consider having a locally negotiated pathway for accessing an old age psychiatry and other appropriate specialist services for those under 65 years for those with a suspected dementia.
7. All healthcare professionals involved in discussing and providing a diagnosis of dementia should be competent in discussing a diagnosis of dementia and knowledgeable about dementia.
8. Those diagnosed with dementia should have a formal assessment of their needs by a health or social care professional with the appropriate knowledge, skills and expertise in dementia.
9. An integrated person-centred package of care inclusive of the person and their family should be developed for these individuals to meet their biopsychosocial-spiritual needs within the prison setting.
10. Those diagnosed with dementia should have a named point of contact, professional or case manager who is a health or social care professional with the appropriate knowledge, skills and expertise in dementia.
11. All prisons should consider implementing a monthly interagency healthcare meeting where these individuals are discussed and reviewed.
12. If advanced dementia care needs cannot be met within the prison setting, early consideration should be given to providing these in a more appropriate location.

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Acknowledgements

Many thanks to all the organisations and individuals who enabled this research or participated in the study sharing their experiences and views.

This project was funded by the Dunhill Medical Trust [grant number RPGF/2006\236] and focussed on improving dementia care in prisons through co-designing an evidence informed dementia care pathway and other practical resources for staff working in Scottish prisons. The study commenced in Spring 2021 and reported in early 2024.

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Glossary

Cognitive or Mild cognitive impairment, often known as MCI, describes a set of symptoms, that produce a decline in mental abilities. The difficulties caused by MCI are worse than would normally be expected for a healthy person of the same age. A person with MCI has mild problems with one or more of the following: memory, reasoning, planning or problem-solving, attention, language and visual depth perception. It is estimated that between 5 and 20% of people aged over 65 have MCI. It is not a type of dementia, but a person with MCI is more likely to go on to develop dementia (Alzheimer's Society, 2023).

Dementia is an umbrella term describing a progressive neurodegenerative syndrome caused by illnesses such Alzheimer's disease that cause structural and chemical changes to the brain. The changes most notably affect memory, orientation, comprehension, calculation, learning capacity, language, and judgement. Consciousness is not affected. The impairment in cognitive function is commonly accompanied, and occasionally preceded, by deterioration in emotional control, social behaviour, or motivation (WHO 2017). As the illness progresses the trajectory is not fixed nor predictable, and people can and do live for months and years with advanced dementia-specific palliative care needs (Reisberg et al 2006) before they reach the stage of dying with dementia.

Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) is a short cognitive screening tool.

Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) is a short cognitive screening tool.

6-item cognitive impairment test (6CIT) is a short cognitive screening tool.

Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination, third revision (ACE)- III, is a more comprehensive cognitive screening tool.

Residential area is the term this report uses for describing the areas in the prison where people in prison were accommodated. The prisons had different names for these areas including hall, wing, unit, flat.

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Practice**

If referring to or using material from this publication please use the following citation
MacRae, R, Tolson, D, Taylor, J, Anderson, K, Chalmers, N, Russ, R and Thompson, L (2024).
The health and social care of people with a diagnosed or suspected dementia living in
prison: Phase 1 report

